

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ROLE OF PCR METHOD IN DIAGNOSTICS OF UROGENITAL INFECTIONS THAT SPREAD RAPIDLY IN MODERN TIMES: EFFECTIVENESS OF STI-8 PANEL

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Abstract

Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) remain a serious challenge for global health systems and have a significant impact on reproductive health, pregnancy outcomes, neonatal outcomes, and public health. Traditional microbiological diagnostic methods often have limited sensitivity and long turnaround times. For this reason, molecular diagnostic methods, especially polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based multiple test panels, are widely used in modern clinical practice. The presented article analyzes the role of the PCR method in the diagnosis of urogenital infections during studies conducted at the TCK of ATU, the clinical significance of the main pathogens included in the STI-8 panel, and the diagnostic effectiveness of this panel with a scientific approach.

Keywords: sexually transmitted infections, Real-Time PCR, multiplex PCR, STI-8 panel

Introduction: Sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) are characterized by hundreds of millions of new infections worldwide each year and pose a serious health risk to women, men, and young people of reproductive age. According to the World Health Organization, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Trichomonas vaginalis*, and *Mycoplasma genitalium* are the most common bacterial and protozoan STI pathogens. [1]. These infections are often asymptomatic and are therefore diagnosed late, resulting in chronic inflammatory processes, infertility, ectopic pregnancy and neonatal complications [2]. Infections of the urogenital tract are transmitted through unprotected vaginal, anal and oral sex, vertical transmission (during pregnancy and childbirth), and rarely through contaminated medical instruments. The clinical symptoms of STDs vary over a wide spectrum: clinical forms such as urethritis, cervicitis, vaginitis, pelvic inflammatory disease, prostatitis, and epididymitis can be observed. However, in a significant proportion of cases, the infection is latent, which is detected only through laboratory tests [3].

The introduction of molecular diagnostics, especially the PCR method, has enabled early and accurate detection of STDs and significantly improved the clinical decision-making process [4].

One of the most important tasks facing modern medicine, especially urology, gynecology and venereology, is the timely detection of infectious and inflammatory diseases of the urogenital tract. Sexually transmitted infections (STIs) are not only an individual health problem, but also a socio-economic burden affecting reproductive health at the global level. According to the latest statistical reports of the World Health Organization (WHO), more than 370 million new cases of treatable STIs (chlamydia, gonorrhea, trichomoniasis, etc.) are registered in the world every year [5].

The clinical picture of urogenital infections has changed significantly in recent decades. If previously these infections manifested themselves with acute symptoms (profuse discharge, severe pain), currently

there is an increase in asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic (subclinical) forms. This "hidden" course leads to late referral of patients to medical care. As a result, infections that are not treated in a timely manner lead to chronic prostatitis, epididymitis and impaired spermatogenesis in men, and pelvic inflammatory disease, ectopic pregnancy and secondary infertility in women [6].

One of the main difficulties in modern diagnostics is "mixed infections" or polymicrobial associations. Often, not just one type of pathogen, but several pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms are simultaneously involved in the inflammatory process in a patient. Although traditional microscopic examination and bacteriological culture methods have high specificity, their sensitivity is insufficient for the detection of many microorganisms (for example, *Mycoplasma genitalium* or *Chlamydia trachomatis*). Also, the bacteriological cultivation method requires a long time (3-7 days), which leads to a delay in treatment [7].

In solving these problems, Real-Time PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) technology has emerged as the "gold standard" in diagnostics. The main advantage of the PCR method is its high analytical sensitivity and specificity; This method can identify the pathogen even when there are only a few copies of its DNA in the biological material [8]. The STI-8 panel (simultaneous determination of 8 pathogens) applied in the laboratory department of the Teaching Surgery Clinic of the Azerbaijan Medical University is one of the most effective forms of this technology. This panel simultaneously screens for both obligate pathogens and opportunistic pathogens (e.g., *Ureaplasma* species) that cause inflammation when present above a certain concentration in a urethral smear. The STI-8 panel detects multiple agents simultaneously, allowing for the detection of co-infections in patients. This allows for a more accurate assessment of the patient's clinical status and selection of an appropriate treatment strategy [9].

Table 1.

Clinical efficacy of the STI-8 Panel		
Pathogen	Main clinical form	Possible complications
<i>Chlamydia trachomatis</i>	Urethritis, cervicitis	Infertility, ectopic pregnancy
<i>Neisseria gonorrhoeae</i>	Gonorrhea, pelvic inflammation	PID, neonatal ophthalmia
<i>Mycoplasma genitalium</i>	Nongonococcal urethritis	Chronic urethritis, infertility
<i>Mycoplasma hominis</i>	Vaginitis, PID	Pregnancy complications
<i>Ureaplasma urealyticum</i>	Urethritis	Premature birth
<i>Ureaplasma parvum</i>	Asymptomatic carriage	Neonatal infections
<i>Trichomonas vaginalis</i>	Vaginitis, urethritis	Increased risk of HIV transmission
<i>Gardnerella vaginalis</i>	Bacterial vaginosis	Pregnancy complications

Table 2.

Comparison of PCR and traditional diagnostic methods		
Indicator	PCR (multiplex)	Cultivation / Microscopy
Sensitivity	High (90–100%)	Medium–Low
Result time	24–48 hours	3–7 days
Detection of co-infection	Possible	Limited
Asymptomatic cases	Effective	Difficult
Indicator	PCR (multiplex)	Cultivation / Microscopy

Scientific studies have shown that multiplex PCR-based STI panels demonstrate 90–100% sensitivity and high specificity. The use of the STI-8 panel: ensures early diagnosis, detection of asymptomatic carriers, selection of targeted antibiotic therapy, and reduction of the risk of relapse and re-infection. The STI-8 panel is of particular clinical importance in pregnant women, patients with infertility problems, and high-risk groups[10].

The aim of the study: To determine the diagnostic efficacy of the STI-8 multiplex PCR panel and the frequency of pathogens in patients with suspected urogenital pathology.

Materials and methods: The research work was carried out in the central laboratory of the Educational Surgical Clinic of the Azerbaijan Medical University (AMU ESC) equipped with modern technological equipment from 10.09.2025 to 25.12.2025. Urethral swab samples taken in accordance with aseptic rules from patients receiving treatment in hospital conditions, as well as from patients who referred to the laboratory with urogenital complaints by a doctor, were used as biological material for the examination. In the presented research study, the results of the application of the STI-8 multiplex PCR test were analyzed, and the diagnostic speed of this method and its role in determining complex treatment tactics were scientifically and practically substantiated.

During the study, samples from 177 patients were processed. The patients who presented were mostly between 25 and 40 years of age, with more infections recorded in men over the age of 30. Samples were collected in sterile transport media, standard aseptic procedures were followed to prevent contamination, and delivered to the laboratory according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Methodological and technical support: The Real-Time PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) method, the latest achievement in molecular genetic diagnostics, was used in the course of the study. This method is

based on the isolation, amplification and real-time detection of specific DNA fragments of pathogenic microorganisms in the biological material under study. The laboratory stage was carried out using fully automated systems, which minimized errors caused by the human factor and ensured a high degree of accuracy of the results. Simultaneous detection of pathogens was ensured using specific primers and fluorescent probes in accordance with the STI-8 panel (table 1).

The thermocycling program included an initial denaturation step followed by 40 amplification cycles. Fluorescence signals were recorded in real time. Positive, negative and internal control samples were used in each test series.

Scientific Basis of the STI-8 Panel: The STI-8 test system used is in a multiplex format and allows you to identify the 8 most dangerous pathogens of the urogenital tract in a single reaction. This includes obligate pathogens (*Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Trichomonas vaginalis*, *Mycoplasma genitalium*) and clinically significant opportunistic pathogens (*Mycoplasma hominis*, *Ureaplasma urealyticum*, *Ureaplasma parvum*, *Gardnerella vaginalis*). Quantitative analysis (titer indicators) is the basis for the assessment of opportunistic microorganisms, which allows for the differentiation of the carrier state from the active inflammatory process.

Statistical analysis: All obtained clinical and laboratory indicators were analyzed using modern statistical software packages, and the percentage of occurrence of each pathogen in the population and the structure of concomitant infections (coinfections) were calculated using mathematical methods. Statistical analysis of the obtained results was carried out using SPSS software. Quantitative indicators were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, and qualitative indicators were expressed as percentage. The prevalence of pathogens was assessed using descriptive statistical methods.

Table 3.

Distribution structure of positive results on the TI-8 Panel by pathogens and gender

Pathogens	Males (n=83)	Females (n=94)	Total (n=177)	Type of Infection
C.trachomatis	5	1	6	Mono-infection
N.gonorrhoeae	5	0	5	Mono-infection
G.vaginalis	3	4	7	Mono-infection
U.parvum	0	1	1	Mono-infection
U.urealyticum	0	1	1	Mono-infection
G.vaginalis + U.urealyticum	0	1	1	Mixed (binary)
U.urealyticum + U.parvum	1	0	1	Mixed (binary)
U.urealyticum + N.gonorrhoeae	1	0	1	Mixed (binary)
U.parvum + G.vaginalis	1	0	1	Mixed (binary)
G.vaginalis + N.gonorrhoeae	1	0	1	Mixed (binary)
G.vaginalis + M.hominis + U.parvum	1	0	1	Mixed (Triplex)
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Total Positive Patient	18	8	26	(14.7%)

Analytical Sensitivity and Specificity. The analytical performance of the STI-8 panel was evaluated based on validation data provided by the manufacturer. The Limit of Detection (LoD) was

determined separately for each pathogen and the results were interpreted based on the Ct (cycle threshold) values.

Conclusion: The results of the study allow us to draw the following conclusions:

High Diagnostic Accuracy: The STI-8 multiplex PCR panel, applied in the laboratory of the ATU Educational-Surgeric Clinic, allowed to identify latent or overt pathogens in 14.7% of patients with urogenital symptoms. The high sensitivity of this method ensures accurate diagnosis of Chlamydia trachomatis and Mycoplasma species, which are difficult to detect with classical methods.

Gender-Different Pathogen Profile: The study showed that while men have a higher incidence of obligate pathogens (especially *N. gonorrhoeae*), women are more likely to have dysbiotic conditions accompanied by an increase in the number of opportunistic pathogens (*Gardnerella*, *Ureaplasma*). This proves the importance of an individual diagnostic approach for both sexes.

Conclusion: The PCR method in the diagnosis of urogenital infections, especially the multiplex real-time PCR-based STI-8 panel, is a modern, reliable and highly informative method in the diagnosis of urogenital infections, one of the most important tools of the modern clinical laboratory. High sensitivity, early detection of STDs, detection of co-infections, rapid turnaround time, and broad pathogen coverage make these tests effective and reliable. This allows for the formulation of early detection and effective treatment strategies, ultimately improving the health outcomes of patients.

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